

MULTISCALE DAMAGE MODELING FOR HIGHLY-FILLED PARTICULATE COMPOSITES: PARTICLE SIZE EFFECT AND COUPLING WITH FINITE STRAINS

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Keywords: *energetic composites, multiscale modeling, microstructure generation, particle size effect, interface debonding, finite strain*

1 Introduction

This work is devoted to the mechanical behavior of highly-filled particulate composites, such as propellant-like materials. This type of materials is composed of an elastomeric matrix and reactive particles (volume fraction greater than 60%) which could react to an accidental or intentional loading with a very large and unexpected energy release leading to the possible destruction of the material and its environment.

Debonding between particles and matrix is a well-known phenomenon in highly-filled particulate composites. For energetic materials, interfacial defects (pores) are the location of chemical reactions leading to the initiation and propagation of combustion within the material. These reactions are moreover influenced by local heat due to mechanical dissipation inherent to strain and damage micromechanisms. Now, reactive models exist in order to predict such events but they require essential input data such as damage configuration (position and morphology of defects) and estimates of local mechanical fields.

The complex morphology and the strongly non-linear behavior of propellant materials (finite strains, interfacial damage, etc.) led to the progressive development of a specific multiscale technique which enables the access to local fields and to the homogenized response. This method, the “Morphological Approach” (M.A.), allows the geometrical representation of granular morphology in an explicit way (particles, intergranular zones, spatial distribution in microstructure) while not meshing the different phases of the composite. The kinematical framework allows a direct solving,

without any prior linearization of local non-linear constitutive laws [1] unlike the Eshelby-based approaches [2]. It avoids questions about the choice of a linearization method.

The modeling of the evolution of damage by particle/matrix debonding leads to the characteristics of defects in the microstructure and induced effects at different scales [3]. Until now, the M.A. in the presence of damage was formulated in the small strain framework, considering the constituents (particles and matrix) as linear elastic.

In this contribution, we will first expose a work with the M.A. as proposed in [3] in order to evaluate its predictive capacities regarding particle size effects and interaction between particles. Indeed, particle size is an important factor governing both mechanical and reactive properties of energetic composites and playing also an important role in damage phenomenology. Debonding in particulate composites shows an important influence of the dimension of particles: debonding occurs preferentially on large particles before occurring on smaller ones [4]. Moreover, there is interaction between particles: the lowest the matrix volume fraction is, the sooner the debonding will occur [5]. Consequently, we will study these effects on different microstructures: unit cells, random monomodal and bimodal microstructures.

Then, we will propose new developments, traducing in the M.A. the important strains that can be undergone by the matrix while modeling debonding. This approach completes the previous ones by combining finite strains behavior (dealt with for undamaged materials [1]) and damage by interfacial debonding (previously investigated in the small strain and rotation framework [3]).

2 The Morphological Approach: microstructure representation and main hypotheses

The considered microstructures are represented by polyhedral grains interconnected by thin matrix layers with uniform thicknesses [1,3,6]. The interfaces of opposite polyhedra are parallel. Considering the microstructure in its initial and non-deformed configuration, the layers α are characterized by four morphological parameters: the thickness of the layer h^α , the projected area A^α , the vector \mathbf{d}^α linking the centroids of the polyhedra which are on both sides of the layer and the unit normal vector \mathbf{n}^α defining the orientation of the grain/layer reference interface (Fig. 1). For random microstructures, the projected area is identified as the average of both areas obtained by projection of both opposite interfaces, from the grains centroids, on the middle plane of the intergranular zone. With these morphological parameters, initial microstructure is represented in an explicit way.

From this geometrical schematization, the M.A. disposes of simplifying kinematical hypotheses. In this way, while (i) the centroids of the grains have a global motion defined by the macroscopic displacement gradient \mathbf{F} (data for the problem), (ii) the grains are supposed to be subjected to a homogeneous displacement gradient \mathbf{f}^0 which is identical for all grains. (iii) Each layer α is subjected to a homogeneous displacement gradient \mathbf{f}^α which can be different from one layer to another. Finally, (iv) local disturbances at grain edges and corners are neglected [3].

3 Evaluation: particle size effect and interaction effect on debonding chronology

After a presentation of theoretical elements about the M.A. formulated in linear elasticity with interface debonding, the particle size influence on damage phenomenology is investigated in the framework of small strains. In this perspective, many evaluations were led, with gradual complexities: first, calculations on periodic microstructures, then on random monomodal microstructures and finally on a random bimodal microstructure.

3.1 Interfacial debonding and evolutive damage in the small strain framework

Interfacial defects into the microstructure are described by relative displacement jumps across the interfaces, while considering a continuous displacement field across the sound interfaces [7]. The kinematical framework exposed above implies that the displacement discontinuity vector across the debonded interface is an affine function of spatial coordinates. This condition does not allow a partial debonding of the interfaces but does not prohibit partial decohesion of a particle which is schematized by a polyhedron with many facets. The assumption of a homogeneous displacement gradient for each grain allows only two possible configurations for a layer α : either no decohesion or simultaneous debonding of both interfaces. This double decohesion can be acceptable only if two opposite parallel interfaces have close geometrical properties: this supplementary constraint has been added to the polyhedrization process.

Consequently, the displacement gradient of a layer α is written depending on the displacement gradient of the grains \mathbf{f}^0 , the macroscopic displacement gradient \mathbf{F} and the morphological data [7]:

$$\mathbf{f}_{ij}^\alpha = \mathbf{f}_{ij}^0 + (\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{f}^0)_{ik} \frac{\mathbf{d}_k^\alpha \mathbf{n}_j^\alpha}{h^\alpha} + \mathbf{f}_{ij}^{\alpha D} \quad (1)$$

The $\mathbf{f}^{\alpha D}$ term represents the specific contribution of the pair of defects at the interfaces of the debonded layer α . If the layer is sound, $\mathbf{f}^{\alpha D} = \mathbf{0}$.

The compatibility between the local motion and the global motion (described by the given displacement gradient \mathbf{F}) is ensured through the following condition to be satisfied by morphological parameters:

$$\frac{1}{|\mathbf{V}|} \sum_{\alpha} \mathbf{d}_i^\alpha \mathbf{n}_j^\alpha A^\alpha = \delta_{ij} \quad (2)$$

where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker symbol and $|\mathbf{V}|$ is the volume of the schematized microstructure. Equation (2) is a criterion of applicability of the M.A. on a given composite and the mean to choose the Representative Volume Element of the microstructure.

The generalized Hill lemma taking into account discontinuities across interfaces leads to:

$$(1-c)\sigma_{ij}^0 + \frac{1}{|\mathbf{V}|} \sum_{\alpha} \sigma_{ij}^\alpha A^\alpha h^\alpha - \frac{1}{|\mathbf{V}|} \sum_{\alpha} t_i^\alpha d_j^\alpha = 0 \quad (3)$$

where $c = \frac{1}{|V|} \sum_{\alpha} A^{\alpha} h^{\alpha}$ is the matrix volume fraction

and $t_i^{\alpha} = \sigma_{ik}^{\alpha} n_k^{\alpha} A^{\alpha}$ is the total force transmitted through the layer α . $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^0$ is the average stress tensor over the volume of the grains and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{\alpha}$ is the average stress tensor over the volume of a layer α .

Considering an elastic linear behavior for the constituents [3], the insertion of local constitutive laws in equation (3) leads, with equations (1) and (2), to an expression in which the main unknown quantity is the displacement gradient of the grains \mathbf{f}^0 . For a fixed damage configuration, there is a given number of open interfacial defects (noted $\alpha = \beta$) and a given number of closed interfacial defects (noted $\alpha = f$). For this study, we only consider open interfacial defects and nucleation. To obtain more details about closed interfacial defects, closure and re-opening of defects, the Reader may consult Dartois and al. [3].

Solving of equation (3) gives the expression of \mathbf{f}^0 depending on the macroscopic displacement gradient \mathbf{F} , morphological parameters $\{\mathbf{d}^{\alpha}, h^{\alpha}, A^{\alpha}, \mathbf{n}^{\alpha}\}$, mechanical properties of constituents and parameters linked to the interfacial damage $\{\mathbf{f}^{\beta D}\}$. The solving and getting \mathbf{f}^0 give the access to \mathbf{f}^{α} for every layer (via equation (1)), local strains and Cauchy stresses, and then homogenized stress.

The strains $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{\beta D}$ due to open defects depend on the imposed macroscopic strain \mathbf{E} . Consequently, their expression have been determined through a complementary homogenization-localization procedure [3,7].

Debonding is only supposed to occur in mode I. Dartois and al. [3] have proposed a nucleation criterion for interfacial defects. Two points P_1 and P_2 are defined on each side of the interface $I^{1\alpha}$ of a layer α before debonding (Fig. 2), respectively into the grain and into the matrix. These two points are each equidistant of a distance λ from their normal projection B_1 on the interface, where B_1 is the gravity centre of $I^{1\alpha}$. Debonding occurs at the interface when the normal projection of the difference of actual positions d_{norm}^{α} of P_1 and P_2 on the normal \mathbf{n}^{α} reaches a certain critical value d_{crit} , so:

$$d_{\text{norm}}^{\alpha} = 2\lambda + \left\{ \left[2\mathbf{f}^0 + (\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{f}^0) \frac{\mathbf{d}^{\alpha} \otimes \mathbf{n}^{\alpha}}{h^{\alpha}} \right] \mathbf{n}^{\alpha} \right\} \mathbf{n}^{\alpha} \quad (4)$$

As soon as a layer α verifies $d_{\text{norm}}^{\alpha} = d_{\text{crit}}$, the opposite interfaces are debonded.

3.2 First evaluations on periodic cells

In order to approach this study with growing difficulties, calculations are performed on periodic microstructures. Consider a cell with a cubic particle of dimension L (Fig. 3). Three layers of matrix are placed on three adjacent facets of this grain. This cell is repeatable with simple translations and allows the building of a periodic composite. Constituents have an isotropic, linear, elastic behavior [3].

Particle size effect:

The studied microstructures are characterized by the same matrix volume fraction and the same damage parameters $(d_{\text{crit}}, \lambda)$. The particle size changes from one unit cell to another. The mechanical loading is an extension in direction 1 whatever the periodic cell which is considered. The extension in direction 1 is associated with transverse contractions in directions 2 and 3. A constant ratio of 0.3 between extension in direction 1 and the transverse contractions is chosen. We try to establish a link between the macroscopic strain imposed in extension when the debonding occurs, and the particle size.

In order to compare several microstructures with constant matrix volume fraction c while the particle size L varies, we impose the thickness h^1 of the layer 1 which stays the same whatever the case studied with a fixed volume fraction. In consequence, the two other thicknesses of layers, supposed to be equal, are formulated:

$$h^2 = h^3 = L \left[\left(\frac{L}{(1-c)(L+h^1)} \right)^{1/2} - 1 \right] \quad (5)$$

The projected areas A^{α} are then evaluated in order to respect the compatibility assumption established in equation (2).

Consequently, the parameters (c, h^1) characterizing the morphology and the damage parameters $(d_{\text{crit}}, \lambda)$ remain constant whatever the compared microstructures. The other morphological parameters (thicknesses of layers h^2 and h^3 , vectors \mathbf{d}^{α} , projected areas A^{α}) are calculated as explained previously, according to the particle size L chosen and the microstructure parameters.

Every periodic cell is subjected to the same extension in direction 1. We observe the

macroscopic strain corresponding to the moment when the matrix debonds from the interface whose normal is collinear to the loading direction (reference layer).

To notice the expected phenomena, a graph represents the macroscopic stress S_{11} in the extension direction, normalized by the maximal stress S_{\max} seen by the periodic cell, vs. the imposed macroscopic strain E_{11} , normalized by the macroscopic strain E_{debond} corresponding to the first periodic cell which undergoes a debonding of the reference layer.

In Fig. 4, the particle size effects can be observed on a periodic cell with 25% of matrix volume fraction and a thickness of the reference layer $h^1 = 20 \mu\text{m}$, for three different particle sizes ($L = 100 \mu\text{m}$, $200 \mu\text{m}$, $400 \mu\text{m}$). As a result, it can be seen that debonding occurs first on the cell with a particle of $400 \mu\text{m}$, then a particle of $200 \mu\text{m}$ and finally a particle of $100 \mu\text{m}$. Consequently, we notice the particle size effect observed by Rae and al. [4], which was also evaluated in a consistent way by Tan and al. until matrix volume fractions of 50% in the high explosive PBX 9501 [8] with the Mori-Tanaka method [9] and a bilinear cohesive law for the particle/matrix.

Interaction between particles:

In order to observe the interaction effect between particles on periodic cells, the same type of study has been performed while fixing the particle size and changing the matrix volume fraction. An uniaxial extension in direction 1 is applied to every generated microstructure. As it was done previously, the damage parameters ($d_{\text{crit},\lambda}$) and the thickness h^1 of the reference layer stay the same whatever the considered periodic cells. The other morphological parameters of the microstructure are evaluated thanks to the data given in the beginning, equation (5) and in order to respect the compatibility assumption given by equation (2). Equation (4) allows one to determine the macroscopic strain corresponding to the moment when the matrix debonds from the interface reference layer/particle.

Fig. 5 shows the particle interaction effects for a periodic cell with a particle size $L = 200 \mu\text{m}$ and a thickness of the reference layer $h^1 = 10 \mu\text{m}$, for three different matrix volume fractions ($c = 15\%$, 25% , 35%). Here again, an order can be seen in the macroscopic strains corresponding to the debonding

of the reference interface of the periodic cells studied. Damage occurs preferentially in the microstructure whose matrix volume fraction is 15%, then 25% and finally 35%. These observations confirm what was noticed by Inglis and al. [5] or Matouš and al. [10]: debonding occurs preferentially on large particles (particle size effect) and in regions where important particle volume fractions are observed (interaction effect).

Conclusion:

The M.A. abilities to reproduce size effects and interaction between particles in periodic particulate composites have been illustrated on simple cases. This modelling approach, adapted to highly-filled composites, succeeds in predicting the expected effects for important particle volume fractions in this particular case, whereas Tan and al. [8,9] carried out simulations with the Mori-Tanaka method adapted to more moderate volume fractions [5]. For step-by-step approach difficulties, we next took an interest in the response of the M.A. to uniaxial extension loadings applied on random monomodal microstructures numerically generated.

3.3 Comparison of random monomodal microstructures numerically generated

The generated microstructures present a more consistent geometry regarding the real materials (Fig. 6). An important particle volume fraction is randomly distributed. The volumes of particles are moderately scattered around an average value, which is the volume of a spherical particle of diameter L . The constituents have a linear, elastic, isotropic behavior [3]. The same uniaxial extension loading is applied whatever the studied microstructure. Each case is characterized by the same damage parameters ($d_{\text{crit},\lambda}$).

The macroscopic axial strains corresponding to the moment when the first debonding occurs into these microstructures is evaluated. Because of the random organization of microstructure, many simulations are performed for each studied configuration and an arithmetic average of macroscopic axial strains corresponding to the first nucleation is made. Three different matrix volume fractions c and three average particle sizes L are considered: nine configurations (c,L) are studied. Ten random generations are performed for each of these

configurations. A summary of this approach appears in Tab. 1.

Fig. 7 shows the results of the average macroscopic strain corresponding to the first interface debonding noticed for every studied configuration (c,L). As Kanit and al. did [11,12], variations between the various simulations of a given configuration are evaluated through the variance. If $\langle z \rangle$ is the arithmetic average of a quantity z over all the realizations, the variance D_z is:

$$D_z^2 = \langle z^2 \rangle - (\langle z \rangle)^2 \quad (6)$$

Consequently, the variation interval around the average value, represented on Fig. 7, is defined by the boundaries $[\langle z \rangle - 2D_z; \langle z \rangle + 2D_z]$.

For a fixed particle size, we notice the expected evolution in debonding chronology when matrix volume fraction changes. Indeed, the most contained the matrix is (important particle volume fraction), the earlier the first nucleation occurs. This is confirmed by literature [5,10]. Moreover, we notice that the amplitude of the variation intervals around the average decreases when the matrix volume fraction decreases (i.e. when the particle volume fraction increases). This observation illustrates the efficiency of the M.A. which is better adapted to high particle volume fractions than the Mori-Tanaka scheme used by Tan and al. [8,9] and evaluated in [5].

For a constant matrix volume fraction, we cannot observe a significant trend of the average macroscopic strain corresponding to the first debonding when the particle size changes. Consequently, it is difficult to say if the M.A. is able to take into account the particle size effect on these random monomodal microstructures. Indeed, the morphologies studied, although they are randomly organized, are strongly similar, because of their monomodal character. It would be necessary to complete this study with a more general simulation campaign, in order to avoid morphologic likeness between every configuration.

3.3 Observation of a random bimodal microstructure numerically generated

In order to evaluate the M.A. abilities to take into account the particle size effect for random microstructures, a random bimodal numerically generated microstructure has been tested. Then, the

nucleation chronology of this microstructure has been studied for a first evaluation of the M.A. ability to deal with expected effects.

The studied microstructure contains more than 7000 particles (volume fraction: 74% - Fig. 8). The average volume of “small grains” (volume fraction: 81%) is the volume of a spherical particle of diameter $L = 200 \mu\text{m}$. The average volume of “large grains” (volume fraction: 19%) is the volume of a spherical particle of diameter $L = 280 \mu\text{m}$. The granular distribution (Fig. 8) is considered on the set of internal particles of the Representative Volume Element: the grains on the edges are considered as incomplete, they only are cut particles in order to create a volume with regular edges.

While keeping the same mechanical properties for the constituents and the same damage parameters (d_{crit}, λ) as in the study on monomodal microstructures, an uniaxial extension in the direction 1 is applied. First results let think that the particle size effect is well-reproduced by the M.A. Indeed, we notice (Tab. 2) that the first debonding occurs on a matrix layer located between two “large grains” (LG in Tab. 2) and that next debondings occur on matrix layers located between two “small grains” (SG in Tab. 2). These observations confirm the expected results.

3.4 Intermediate conclusion

With this study, we have tried to evaluate the predictive abilities of the M.A. in the small strain framework. In this way, only one non-linearity is considered: interface debonding.

The particle size effect was observed on simple periodic microstructures and generalized on a random bimodal microstructure. It allowed us to confirm the observations made in literature [4].

On the other hand, results show the capacities of the M.A. to take into account the complex interaction effects between the grains, thanks to the description of heterogeneity into the matrix.

In the sequel, further developments on the M.A are presented, aiming at considering both interfacial debonding in the studied materials and the large strains that can undergo the matrix.

4 Non-linearities coupling: finite strains and damage

The hypotheses about the microstructure schematization and the kinematical description have been introduced in Section 2, but in the small strain framework [3]. Now, the developments are performed in finite transformations, in a Lagrangian spirit. As a result, \mathbf{F} , \mathbf{f}^0 and \mathbf{f}^α refer now respectively to the macroscopic transformation gradient, the transformation gradient of the grains and the transformation gradient of a layer.

Moreover, the assumption about the affine form of the displacement discontinuity vector across a debonded interface in relation to the spatial coordinates exposed in Section 3.1 is retained. Therefore, no partial debonding is allowed along an interface: both interfaces are debonded or the layer is sound.

4.1 Localization-homogenization problem approach and insertion of local constitutive laws

With the same methodology presented in Section 3.1 and in [7], the conditions on displacement discontinuity across interfaces lead to an expression of the transformation gradient of a layer α depending on the global transformation gradient \mathbf{F} , the transformation gradient of the grains \mathbf{f}^0 , and morphological data:

$$\mathbf{f}_{ij}^\alpha = \mathbf{f}_{ij}^0 + (\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{f}^0)_{ik} \frac{\mathbf{d}_k^\alpha \mathbf{n}_j^\alpha}{h^\alpha} + \mathbf{f}_{ij}^{\alpha D} \quad (7)$$

The $\mathbf{f}^{\alpha D}$ term represents the specific contribution of the pair of defects at the interfaces of the debonded layer α . If the layer is sound, $\mathbf{f}^{\alpha D} = \mathbf{0}$.

The compatibility between the local motion and the global motion (described by the given displacement gradient \mathbf{F}) is ensured through the following condition to be satisfied by morphological parameters:

$$\frac{1}{|V_0|} \sum_{\alpha} \mathbf{d}_i^\alpha \mathbf{n}_j^\alpha A^\alpha = \delta_{ij} \quad (8)$$

where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker symbol and $|V_0|$ is the initial volume of the microstructure. Like in the small strain framework with equation (2), equation (8) is a criterion of applicability of the M.A. on a given composite and the mean to choose the Representative Volume Element of the microstructure.

The generalized Hill lemma leads to an equation depending on the nominal stress:

$$(1-c) \mathbf{s}_{ij}^{*0} + \frac{1}{|V_0|} \sum_{\alpha} \mathbf{s}_{ij}^{*\alpha} A^\alpha h^\alpha - \frac{1}{|V_0|} \sum_{\alpha} \mathbf{t}_j^\alpha \mathbf{d}_i^\alpha = 0 \quad (9)$$

where $c = \frac{1}{|V_0|} \sum_{\alpha} A^\alpha h^\alpha$ is the matrix volume fraction in the reference configuration and $\mathbf{t}_j^\alpha = \mathbf{s}_{kj}^{*\alpha} \mathbf{n}_k^\alpha A^\alpha$ is the total force transmitted through the layer α at the instant t , written in the reference configuration. \mathbf{s}^{*0} is the average nominal stress tensor over the volume of the grains and $\mathbf{s}^{*\alpha}$ is the average nominal stress tensor over the volume of a layer α .

For the sake of simplicity, an hyperelastic behavior for the constituents of the particulate composite is chosen in a first step, namely a Neo-Hooke law with a distortion-volume decoupling (formulation with modified invariants of the right Cauchy-Green tensor). We impose an important contrast between matrix and grains, taking into account the fact that the particles constitute a quasi-rigid phase in the material for the low loading rate considered. The closed defects are supposed to be blocked by infinite friction as in previous studies [3,7].

Introducing local constitutive laws in equation (9) with (7) leads to an equation (10) composed of three terms: Φ^α associated to every layer α in the microstructure, Φ^β related to the layers with open interfacial defects (layers β), Φ^f related to the layers with closed interfacial defects (layers f).

Each of these terms depends on many parameters, with strong non-linearity. For each of these parameters, the “0” exponent refers to grains, and the “ α ”, “ β ” and “ f ” exponents have the same significance than above. C_{10}^0 and C_{10}^α are Neo-Hooke coefficients for grains and matrix, K^0 and K^α are the bulk moduli associated to both phases. $|V_0|$ is the initial total volume of the microstructure and nc^x is a parameter indicating the number of layers associated to the “ x ” exponent (α , β or f). The morphological data h^α , A^α , the vector \mathbf{d}^α and the unit normal vector \mathbf{n}^α intervene in each term of (10). Moreover, the three terms depend on the global transformation gradient \mathbf{F} , input for the problem. We finally spot the unknown quantities to be determined in equation (10): the transformation gradient of the grains \mathbf{f}^0 and all the terms $\{\mathbf{f}^{\alpha D}\}$ linked to the

contribution of defects into the microstructure. When the layer α is sound, $\mathbf{f}^{\alpha D} = 0$. When it has open interfacial defects, $\mathbf{f}^{\alpha D} = \mathbf{f}^{\beta D}$. When it has closed interfacial defects, $\mathbf{f}^{\alpha D} = \mathbf{f}^{fD}$.

$$\begin{aligned} & \Phi_{ij}^{\alpha} [C_{10}^{\alpha}, C_{10}^{\alpha}, K^{\alpha}, K^{\alpha}, |V_0|, nc^{\alpha}, h^{\alpha}, A^{\alpha}, \mathbf{d}^{\alpha}, \mathbf{n}^{\alpha}, \mathbf{F}, \mathbf{f}^0, \mathbf{f}^{\alpha D}] \\ & + \Phi_{ij}^{\beta} [C_{10}^{\alpha}, K^{\alpha}, |V_0|, nc^{\beta}, h^{\beta}, A^{\beta}, \mathbf{d}^{\beta}, \mathbf{n}^{\beta}, \mathbf{F}, \mathbf{f}^0, \mathbf{f}^{\beta D}] \quad (10) \\ & + \Phi_{ij}^f [C_{10}^{\alpha}, K^{\alpha}, |V_0|, nc^f, h^f, A^f, \mathbf{d}^f, \mathbf{n}^f, \mathbf{F}, \mathbf{f}^0, \mathbf{f}^{fD}] = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, there are numerous unknown quantities: the transformation gradient of the grains \mathbf{f}^0 , the terms $\{\mathbf{f}^{\beta D}\}$ linked to the nc^{β} layers with open defects, and the terms $\{\mathbf{f}^{fD}\}$ linked to the nc^f layers with closed defects. So, there are $\{1 + nc^{\beta} + nc^f\}$ unknowns. In this way, it is necessary to add equations in order to solve the localization-homogenization problem. Getting the aforementioned unknown terms will allow us to obtain the heterogeneous transformation gradient in the matrix via (7), the nominal stresses field and then, the nominal macroscopic stress by volume averaging.

4.2 Solving ingredients

The assumption of an infinite friction coefficient on the lips of closed defects prevents sliding and implies that these closed defects are blocked into the considered volume. Consequently, the term \mathbf{f}^{fD} for every layer with closed interfacial defects cannot depend on the macroscopic transformation gradient \mathbf{F} . Moreover, according to this assumption, the nucleation of defects is supposed to occur only in a normal mode: the defects are necessarily open before being closed. As a result, the term \mathbf{f}^{fD} is calculated when the closure occurs:

$$\mathbf{f}^{fD} = \mathbf{f}_{\text{closure}}^{\beta D} \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbf{f}_{\text{closure}}^{\beta D}$ is the value of $\mathbf{f}^{\beta D}$ at the moment of defect closure.

On the contrary, $\mathbf{f}^{\beta D}$ depends on the loading and then on the macroscopic transformation gradient \mathbf{F} . As it was done in previous studies [3], this dependency is supposed to be of the same form for every layer β and is searched so that:

$$\mathbf{S}^* = \frac{\partial W}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \quad (12)$$

where $W = \langle w \rangle_{|V_0|}$ is the macroscopic free energy and $\mathbf{S}^* = \langle \mathbf{s}^* \rangle_{|V_0|}$ is the macroscopic nominal stress.

Finally, the morphological and kinematical representation implies that the average displacement discontinuity vectors across the interfaces are opposite (see Dartois and al. [3] for more details). It leads to an expression for every layer with open defects in order to help solving.

Equation (10) and elements (11)-(12) should, after a solving, offer us the access to the unknown elements \mathbf{f}^0 , $\{\mathbf{f}^{\beta D}\}$ and $\{\mathbf{f}^{fD}\}$. We suppose each of these terms being linear during the calculation increments that have to be chosen small enough. The numerical solving process will be based on Newton-Raphson algorithm.

4.3 Nucleation criterion and closure of defects

The problem solving as it is exposed until now only allows determining the damaged material behavior with a fixed damage configuration. In order to take into account the evolution of damage configuration, the formulation has to be completed by a nucleation and a closure criterion for the defects.

The nucleation criterion proposed by Dartois et al. [3] is now extended to finite transformations. In the small strains framework, the normal of the reference interface of a layer was supposed to be invariant. In the finite transformation framework, we can no longer assume this hypothesis: it is necessary to consider the actual normal of the interface.

We consider the same schematization as described in section 3.1 and Fig. 2. The difference of displacement $\Delta \mathbf{U}$ between the two points P_1 and P_2 has the following expression:

$$\Delta \mathbf{U} = \left[2(\mathbf{f}^0 - \mathbf{Id}) + (\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{f}^0) \frac{\mathbf{d}^{\alpha} \otimes \mathbf{n}^{\alpha}}{h^{\alpha}} \right] \lambda \mathbf{n}^{\alpha} \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{Id} is the second order identity tensor.

Debonding happens at the interface when the normal projection of the difference of actual positions of P_1 and P_2 on the current normal \mathbf{n}^{α} reaches a given critical value. Consequently, we observe the evolution of the quantity:

$$d_{\text{norm}}^{\alpha} = (2\lambda \mathbf{n}^{\alpha} + \Delta \mathbf{U}) \cdot \mathbf{n}^{\alpha} \quad (14)$$

The current normal is calculated from a small area element of the initial interface $I^{1\alpha}$ whose normal is \mathbf{n}^{α} . The transported surface element is calculated at the time t ; its current normal is \mathbf{n}^{α} . We obtain:

$$\mathbf{n}^{\alpha} = \frac{\mathbf{f}^0 \mathbf{V}^{1\alpha} \wedge \mathbf{f}^0 \mathbf{V}^{2\alpha}}{\|\mathbf{f}^0 \mathbf{V}^{1\alpha}\| \times \|\mathbf{f}^0 \mathbf{V}^{2\alpha}\| \times |\sin(\mathbf{f}^0 \mathbf{V}^{1\alpha}, \mathbf{f}^0 \mathbf{V}^{2\alpha})|} \quad (15)$$

where $\mathbf{V}^{1\alpha}$ and $\mathbf{V}^{2\alpha}$ are two unit vectors with directions defined from the gravity centre B_1 to two tops of the facet $I^{1\alpha}$ and in order to constitute a direct orthonormal system with the initial normal \mathbf{n}^α (Fig. 9).

To define the closure of defects, we use the local displacement discontinuity across the reference interface $\langle \mathbf{b}^\beta \rangle_{I^{1\beta}}$. Defects are closed when:

$$\langle \mathbf{b}^\beta \rangle_{I^{1\beta}} \cdot \mathbf{n}^{1\beta} = 0 \quad (16)$$

While (16) is positive, the defects remain open.

5 Conclusion

This work on the coupling of two non linearities into the M.A. approach reaches the stage of numerical implementation. First, the localization-homogenization problem will be numerically solved for the sound material case. The results will be compared with those obtained in Nadot-Martin and al. studies [1]. As a consequence, the defects contribution will be ignored in equations (10) to (12). Then, it will be completed with the terms taking into account the influence of open and closed defects in the microstructure, and the Newton-Raphson algorithm will be enhanced in order to get the additional unknown quantities. Nucleation and closure criteria will be incorporated into the solving process. Finally, we will set up the extraction of local and macroscopic data. Thanks to these, we will be able to analyze the different phenomena occurring under different mechanical loadings in order to approve the model.

Concerning the study on particle size effect, it seems necessary to complete the study of random monomodal microstructures with more general microstructures, in order to confirm the M.A. ability to reproduce expected effects.

Fig. 1. Morphological parameters characterizing a layer α

Fig. 2. Schematization and parameters to define nucleation (reference configuration)

Fig. 3. Periodic cell

MULTISCALE DAMAGE MODELING FOR HIGHLY-FILLED PARTICULATE COMPOSITES: PARTICLE SIZE EFFECT AND COUPLING WITH FINITE STRAINS

Fig. 4. Particle size effect on a periodic cell (matrix volume fraction $c = 25\%$; thickness of the reference layer $h^1 = 20 \mu\text{m}$)

Fig. 5. Interaction between particles on a periodic cell (particle size $L = 200 \mu\text{m}$; thickness of the reference layer $h^1 = 10 \mu\text{m}$)

Fig. 6. Random monomodal numerically generated microstructure ($c = 40\%$)

Fig. 7. Particle size effect and interaction on random monomodal microstructures

Fig. 8. Granulometry distribution of the random bimodal microstructure studied

Fig. 9. Unit vectors used to define the actual normal

Matrix volume fraction c	Average particle size L (μm)
0.55	100
	200
	400
0.40	100
	200
	400
0.25	100
	200
	400

Tab. 1. Cases studied for calculations on random monomodal microstructures

Macroscopic strain when interface debonds	Volume of adjacent grain n°1 (mm ³)		Volume of adjacent grain n°2 (mm ³)	
	SG	LG	SG	LG
1.057 10 ⁻³	0.0146		0.0137	
1.102 10 ⁻³	0.0034		0.0035	
1.135 10 ⁻³	0.0038		0.0036	
1.135 10 ⁻³	0.0042		0.0037	
1.135 10 ⁻³	0.0032		0.0039	
1.142 10 ⁻³	0.0029		0.0034	

Tab. 2. First results for a uniaxial extension on a random bimodal microstructure (SG = small grains ; LG = large grains)

Funding Acknowledgments

This study is financially supported by Direction Générale pour l'Armement and Région Poitou-Charentes through Marion Trombini's PhD grant.

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